

DEVELOPING THE METHODOLOGY OF ENGLISH READING

Nurimova Ayzada Razatdinovna,

A student of the faculty of foreign languages and literature,
Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

Annotation: This paper discusses the present method of developing the reading in the context of receptive skills, point out importance, and emphasize the need for receptive skills, students' acquisition for professional as well as pragmatic excellence.

Key words: skills, reading, language, text, information, method, receptive, presentation, material, develop.

When learning a new language, learners tend to develop their receptive skills first and then acquire productive capability. It is a complex relationship between the two as they all play a supporting role with developing other skills. For example, reading skills can be a supporting factor to the development of writing, whereas listening can improve speaking fluency.

Developing receptive skills can be particularly challenging especially when communicating with a fluent or native speaker. Although starting a conversation may be done with relative ease, maintaining one poses greater challenges. In a lesson when the teacher's aim is to develop receptive skills, the first step to do is to introduce the topic of reading. When we choose a text, we are to activate the predictive skills of our students. The learners are expected to extract the specific information from the text and they are expected to find out one or two facts.

That is the reason why we always have to set pre-reading/pre-listening tasks before reading or listening. At this stage, the teacher aims to focus the students' attention on certain facts mentioned in the reading. The next purpose of the teacher will be to sustain the students' attention while they are reading the extract. As a while

reading task, a teacher can ask the students to underline certain words or phrases or on hearing, certain facts or data the students can clap or raise their hands. After reading a text, the students are expected to do some post reading tasks. They have to get the general picture, which means that they have to infer the opinion or attitude of the writer or the speaker. The ability to infer opinion and attitude is largely based on the recognition of linguistic style and its use to achieve appropriate purposes. Another post-reading task for the teacher can be to make students deduce meaning from context.

Very often, the reader is involved in the use of reading for the sole purpose of extracting specific information. In other words, the reader, for example, may look at a piece of written language not in order to understand it all, but for finding out only one or two facts. He may quickly read a film review only to find out the name of the star. The listener may turn on the radio and listen only for a particular item of news that he wants to hear. In both cases, the reader will disregard everything except the information he is interested in.

The point is that the deducing of meaning is important for a language user who will often mean unknown words and we will try to train students in the same way to guess the meaning of unknown words. Teachers can make students recognize discourse markers, styles and registers as well. It is important for the teachers to develop students' discourse competence in addition to their linguistic/grammatical competence as well. Teachers are also expected to focus on the intercultural aspects of language teaching. Social-linguistic competence of students can be developed in this way.

Most likely learners may not recognize features of connected speech or idiomatic language, which may lead to an unsuccessful interaction.

If the language or grammar is too complicated, it makes the text be unintelligible. The key of reading is that when learners read information, they have much less support than when they are working with the written word on the page.

The best way to improve receptive skills is from exposure whether from an enjoyable authentic text or a quality ESL textbook. For example, television, music, books and magazines are great ways to build vocabulary while incidentally promoting learner autonomy. Course books can provide a basic scaffold and are adapted for an ESL learner, whereas authentic materials provide exposure to real language use.

However, authentic materials can demotivate learners if the materials are not appropriately graded or applicable to their interests. It is an important consideration to choose material, which is not too difficult or easy, and which relates culturally, so adaptation is an important consideration for teachers. Equally important are effectively staging a reading or listening lesson to maximize output. The below staging is an effective way to teach either a listening or reading lesson.

List of used literature

1. Afflerbach, P., Pearson, D., & Paris, S. (2008). Clarifying differences between reading skills and reading strategies.
2. Blair, T., Rupley, W., & Nichols, W. (2007). The effective teacher of reading: Considering the “what” and “how” of instruction.
3. Booth, D. (2001). Reading and writing in the middle years.
4. Chall, J. (1983). Stages of reading development. N.Y: McGraw- Hill Book Company.